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“DRIFTING SPACES”

We danced with golden glow
Our hands perfectly fit,
Each glance a secret language
Of love and warm commit

Laughter tangled in the air
Dreams of being together woven tightly
Perfectly with each other.

We thought our bond was unbreakable
For our love true and pure.
For time witness our love endures
Of every misfit adventures.

Our heat beats in syncopation,
A rhythm so pure.
We swore to hold each other,
sure and secure.

But whispers grew to walls
Unspoken words took its roots.
For we are scared to hurt each other
Of the misfits we encounter.

Misunderstandings blooms
Where honest talks could end it all.
I hid my fear of falling,
you masked yours with ignorance.

Asking me you need for space
For you to breathe again.

We read each other wrong,
Lost in a hazy speculated embrace.

A text misread, a sigh misheard,
Gaps, widened day by day,
Transparency should clear our way,
But it becomes a stranger chasing us away.

Now, we walked on a parallel path,
No longer side by side
Our once-bright flame grew dim,
Swallowed by pride and shame.

I took your silence for rejection,
You took mine for hesitation and doubt.
We keep our truths locked tight,
Shut each other out.

For we are scared that our doubts
Becomes a truth that slaps our face.
The love we'd nurtured faded,
Frayed by unmet needs.

A story of what was,
And no longer fits the needs.

Now sometimes in the dusk,
I catch your gaze across the way,
A flicker of old longing,
a chance to rephrase and say:

"I feared I wasn't enough,
you crave for a moment to be free."

A question before we sign
Our name on writing
To end us permanently.

Tears fall, we talk
We forgive each other imperfection.
We let our truth break free
For our love is stronger than thee,

Perhaps the frayed threads still can be weave,
If we dare to start anew,

To speak with open hearts and respect
To make our love feel true.

